

***The Aims of Education*—Alfred North Whitehead’s Ideas on Education and Learning Revisited After 100 Years**

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The education of a human being is a most complex topic, which we have hardly begun to understand. The only point on which I feel certain is that there is no widespread, simple solution. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 9)

Introduction

The aim of this article is to take the reader on a guided tour of Alfred North Whitehead’s thoughts and concepts concerning education and learning. Although he published his most influential work in this context—*The Aims of Education and Other Essays*—nearly a century ago, his insights remain strikingly relevant today. Yet despite their enduring significance, Whitehead himself and his philosophy of education remains relatively little known.

A. N. Whitehead is primarily known for his fundamental work on mathematics, *Principia Mathematica*, written together with Bertrand Russell (his former student). *Principia Mathematica* is a three-volume work on the foundations of mathematics, published between 1910 and 1913. In a smaller circle, among specialist philosophers and theologians, he is also known as a philosopher and especially as a metaphysician for his concept of process philosophy. In *Process and Reality* (1929/1978) Whitehead developed a distinctive and original model of process philosophy (process thought and process metaphysics) influenced by concepts from Hegel, Bergson, James, Dewey and the—at that time—latest developments in physics (General Theory of Relativity and Quantum Theory). This book also contains his probably most famous and widely known quote: “The safest general characterization of the European philosophical tradition is that it consists of a series of footnotes to Plato” (Whitehead, 1929/1978, p. 39). The quote can be read as a criticism of European academic philosophy at the beginning of the 20th century. Whitehead compared its status with that of the deadlocked medieval scholasticism of around 1400. He saw his three books, *Science and The Modern World*, *Process and Reality*, and *Adventure of Ideas*, as an intellectual exploration of a New World surpassing the philosophical deadlock (Whitehead, 1933, p. 6-7), especially in the field of Natural Philosophy and Metaphysics.

Whitehead experienced and argued against a similar stagnation in his own time, serving as an academic teacher in the field of education and working in universities. For instance, he campaigned in vain for the full admission of women to Cambridge University around the 1890s (Whitehead, 1896). He felt that the traditional universities, especially Oxford and Cambridge, had developed into rather backward-looking institutions, rigid in their educational aims and forms. Whitehead was convinced that academic institutions could only preserve an evolving, vibrant culture and scientific progress by avoiding dogmatism. He felt they had to be constantly

challenged (Hampe, 1998, p. 21). The situation, which he personally perceived as an academic standstill, and in particular as the institutional neglect of empirical sciences, finally prompted him to move from Cambridge to London.

There, first as a lecturer in (applied) mathematics and physics at the University College, and later as Professor at the Imperial College for Science and Technology, Whitehead was successful in establishing new academic institutions such as experimental-polytechnical training centres. He was also involved in teacher training and held a number of administrative positions where he worked to develop technical education and reform university education in general.

The interplay and interlocking of theoretical and application-oriented elements within the framework of study programmes was of central importance to him throughout his whole academic career, especially in an environment that still was traditionally and conservatively theoretically oriented, with a curriculum and teaching philosophy tracing back to the mid-19th century. He writes,

The students are alive, and the purpose of education is to stimulate and guide their self-development. It follows as a corollary from this premiss, that the teachers also should be alive with living thoughts. (Whitehead, 1929, p. v)

This quote from the introduction to his book *The Aims of Education* can be seen as an education-oriented summary of Whitehead's philosophy. The language shows that his roots are in mathematics. The word 'corollary' points to the aliveness of teachers as a by-product of the stated purpose of education. The aliveness of pupils and teachers indicates the experience and (indirectly) the process orientation of Whitehead's philosophy. And stimulation and guidance give a hint to a relational, student-teacher configuration in the setting of formal education, where students and teachers stand each in relation to themselves and also in relation to each other, with the goal to stimulate and guide self-development. Of course, one needs to know a little about Whitehead's philosophy to make such a reading of the quote. Whitehead's work shows a high degree of coherence in terms of content.

In *Principia Mathematica* Whitehead and Russell introduced a specific notation of the theory of classes (sets) and relations (connections between elements of classes). Establishing the importance of relations between elements of logical or mathematical structures was a fundamental step in his metaphysical conception, in which processes and their development through processes rather than dualistic Cartesian ontology (*res cogitans*, *res extensa*) play a central role. (In simple terms, Whitehead interprets processes as the fundamental ontological entity and as the driving force of development). Thus, according to Whitehead, a lively relation between students and teachers is an expression of life in general.

In addition to this programmatic statement, the preface to *The Aims of Education* contains a second sentence that can be read as Whitehead's mission statement as an academic teacher and an educator. As he puts it, "The whole book is a protest against dead knowledge, that is to say, against inert ideas" (Whitehead, 1929, p. v)

Dead knowledge and inert ideas are the antithesis of processes and a lively development, one core not only of Whitehead's philosophy, but also of his professional biography. Twice in his academic life he felt trapped in a backward-looking, structure-bound academic environment. From Cambridge (as described above) he moved to London in 1910. There, he held academic positions in the field of (applied) mathematics and increasingly took on important functions in academic self-administration (Dean of the Faculty of Science at the University of London, member of the University of London's Senate, and Chairman of the Senate's Academic Council). Thus, he was able to promote reforms, but he was also increasingly integrated into existing viscous academic structures and had less and less time for scientific activities. In order to concentrate more fully on philosophy, he accepted the offer from Harvard University to join the faculty as a professor of philosophy. The already 63-year-old Whitehead moved with his family to the United States.

At Harvard, he brought with him the weight of a long and accomplished academic life. It became the foundation for his following major philosophical publications from 1924 on: *Science and the Modern World* (1925), *Process and Reality* (1929), *Adventures of Ideas* (1933), and *Modes of Thought* (1938).

With his concept of process philosophy, Whitehead offers an alternative interpretation to both Cartesian ontology and, for example, the Heideggerian approach of a question-oriented phenomenology and ontology. What Whitehead and Heidegger share can be described as a linguistic struggle for a precise verbal description of complex (ontological) relations. Thus, both use a peculiar, creative language with semantically charged words (e.g., the term 'entity'). That makes Whitehead's major works quite challenging to read. It usually takes several attempts and a comprehensive examination of his concepts to fully understand his thoughts and argumentation. In Blasius's (1997) words, "It must be admitted that much of Whitehead's philosophy is complicated and is in fact quite difficult" (p. 303).

But this is certainly not the case in his essays on education collected in his 1929 book *The Aims of Education and Other Essays*. Most of the essays and addresses were intended for a wider audience, such as teachers, academics, and people working in education. To completely understand the ideas discussed in the book in their full scope, a knowledge of the philosophical work may be helpful. But it is certainly not necessary to understand the primary concern as well as the argumentation and the essential connections.

What characterises Whitehead is his 'mathematical' writing style. For instance, he defines education as "the acquisition of the art of the utilisation of knowledge" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 4). In the following paragraphs, he then unfolds, explains, and further develops his understanding of this definition (or rather characterization) of education. Each of the essays can be read coherently and is characterised by a clear thread of argumentation.

I suppose that the very specific date of publication, 1929, is one major reason for the relatively limited response to this book. *The Aims of Education* was published parallel to Whitehead's main work *Process and Reality*, which is, like his other major philosophical books, quite difficult to read. So, the author's name and the reception of his thoughts as being challenging probably led to a similar assessment of his book on education. This is all the more unfortunate given that some of the concepts developed and discussed in the articles of *The Aims of Education* were far ahead of

their time and only found their way into educational science discourse much later. To name some of the ideas and concepts, a thorough reading shows that Whitehead discusses a well elaborated, culturally embedded notion of stage concept (Chapter II, Chapter III), self-similarity (Chapter II, p. 19, p. 27), education as a process (Chapters I, II III, and VIII), and also of the importance of creativity (Chapters I, II, and VII), curriculum design (Chapters I-III, Chapters IV-VI), fundamental ideas (Chapter I, p. 10), learning-process-centred approaches to the tension between freedom and discipline (Chapter III), and the importance of mental constructions (Chapters II, III, and VIII). Well known learning theorists developed these concepts some decades later; Bandura since the 1940s, Bruner from the late 1950s on, and Piaget, especially in the 1960s, to name some of them.

Whitehead's reputation as a difficult author to read may have been one reason why this book was and is not more widely received in the field of education. Another reason may be that, in contrast to his mathematical and philosophical subject areas, he did not leave behind his thoughts on education in a coherent text. *The Aims of Education* is a collection of essays and addresses, as Whitehead states: "The separate chapters have ... been delivered as addresses at various conferences of educational bodies and of scientific societies" (Whitehead, 1929, p. v). His main thoughts are discussed in the first three chapters, "The Aims of Education," "The Rhythm of Education," and "The Rhythmic Claims of Freedom and Discipline." They do not all contradict each other, but were written at different times for different specific purposes. Therefore, one has to reconstruct the "big picture" from the individual chapters based upon cross-references in terms of content. The individual chapters do provide an easily understandable presentation of the respective ideas. At the same time, however, one reading does not seem to be enough to fully grasp the connections between the chapters, especially with regard to the underlying overall ideas. For instance, Whitehead develops a concrete idea of the necessary basic design of a curriculum, in which he considers developmental psychology, content, and didactic aspects in relation to the entire educational programme and the course of education. The ideas are spread over Chapters I, II, and III and contextualised in Chapters I and VIII with some specific parts on subjects being elaborated on in Chapters IV, V, and VI. The task for the reader is, therefore, to collect and collate the various parts of the concept from the different chapters to obtain an overall picture and understanding.

Assuming that Whitehead compiled the book himself, the following logic of the sequence of chapters can be surmised: as is often the case in his approach, he begins with practical questions, builds on experience and findings, suggests models and concepts, and becomes increasingly generalising and abstract. This becomes clear if we compare the first chapter, an address to non-specialists on the aims of education, with the last, which is closely linked to his philosophy of process.

Furthermore, we can identify a subdivision consisting of chapters that are rather closely related to each other. Chapters I to III provide a coherent general introduction to his ideas and concepts. The following chapters, IV to VII, focus on specific fields and the institutions of formal education. He starts here with a study of his recently completed area, reflecting his time in London at the College of Science and Technology and his role in the Faculty of Science at the University of London (Chapter IV, "Technical Education and Its Relation to Science and Literature"), which is significant as regards the compilation of the book in 1929. The next three chapters follow

Whitehead's own educational and professional path, from a classics-oriented school education (Chapter V, "The Place of Classics in Education") to the study mathematics at university (Chapter VI, "The Mathematical Curriculum"), to his own scientific work as a researcher and teacher at universities (Chapter VII, "Universities and their Functions"). Chapters VIII to X then focus on thinking and thoughts in general, the (exemplary) structure of scientific ideas, and the very general philosophical question of how all this is related to the universe.

In the following, I will provide an overview, accompanied by additional explanatory notes, in order to illuminate Whitehead's philosophy of education. I divide the discussion into three sections, following the layout described above (i.e., Chapters I-III in section 1, Chapters IV-VII in section 2, and Chapters VIII-X in section 3).

The Aims of Education

1. Chapters I – III: Aims, Rhythm, and Rhythmic Claims

1.1. Chapter I – "The Aims of Education"

In this chapter, Whitehead discusses his basic concept of education and learning. His position can be interpreted as a somewhat updated version of Humboldt's concept of *Bildung* (cf. Bacher, 2024), although he does not explicitly mention Humboldt's name:

What we should aim at producing is men who possess both culture and expert knowledge in some special direction. Their expert knowledge will give them the ground to start from, and their culture will lead them as deep as philosophy and as high as art. We have to remember that the valuable intellectual development is self-development.... (Whitehead, 1929, p. 1)

Whitehead advocates for a transformative approach in education that prioritizes the cultivation of knowledge through both practical application and specialized study. He criticizes the (at that time) reigning focus on inert ideas—concepts taught without context or application—which led to a lack of engagement and understanding among students.

Based upon this stance, he then argues for the importance of integrating theoretical ideas with their practical uses within the curriculum, in order to maintain the vitality of knowledge. This approach requires considering the unique capabilities of the teacher, the nature of the students, and the specific opportunities provided by the school's environment.

As the quote shows, Whitehead frames education as a process of self-development with crucial periods. The role of early education is also emphasized as foundational. The overall aim of education should be to produce individuals who are culturally aware and possess expert knowledge in a particular field.

With regard to the organization of learning at schools and universities, Whitehead strongly criticizes uniform external examinations, which fail to account for the individual needs of schools and students, and instead advocates that schools develop their own curricula based on their specific

circumstances. The author calls for educational reform that views the school as the central unit of change, with a curriculum that has been evolved by its own staff and tailored to its needs.

For readers familiar with his process philosophy, Whitehead's ontological approach shines through. The text is driven by his concepts of activity, creativity, and relational development. Surprisingly, in this context he comes to similar conclusions as do reform pedagogues such as Maria Montessori (stressing the importance of teachable moments and the here and now):

The mind is never passive; it is a perpetual activity, delicate, receptive, responsive to stimulus. You cannot postpone its life until you have sharpened it. Whatever interest attaches to your subject-matter must be evoked here and now; whatever powers you are strengthening in the pupil, must be exercised here and now; whatever possibilities of mental life your teaching should impart, must be exhibited here and now. That is the golden rule of education, and a very difficult rule to follow. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 9)

Furthermore (and without going into further detail), Whitehead stresses the importance of beauty and aesthetics in education.

1.2. Chapter II – “The Rhythm of Education”

Whitehead's rhythmic concept of education describes what later became popular as the idea of the stage concept in developmental psychology and educational science (cf. Bruner, 1960; Piaget, 1971; Havighurst, 1972; Bandura, 1977):

The principle is merely this—that different subjects and modes of study should be undertaken by pupils at fitting times when they have reached the proper stage of mental development. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 24)

Thus, he emphasizes the importance of aligning educational content and methods with the natural developmental stages of a student's mental growth. Whitehead criticizes the traditional linear progression of subjects without considering the psychological readiness of students and suggests that education should follow a rhythmic cycle consisting of three stages: romance, precision, and generalization.

1. ***The Stage of Romance***: this stage is characterized by a child's initial excitement about and engagement with new knowledge, where facts and ideas are encountered with a sense of wonder and novelty. In an adequate didactic environment, this stage is characterized by a vividness of new knowledge and an exploration of its unexplored connections and possibilities. This stage is not dominated by systematic procedure, but by immediate cognizance of fact.
2. ***The Stage of Precision***: here, the focus shifts to exactness and detailed understanding. It involves systematic analysis and the addition of new knowledge that fits into this analysis. This stage is akin to learning the grammar of a language or science, where students are expected to understand and apply a given way of analysing facts.

3. ***The Stage of Generalisation***: in this final stage the knowledge and skills acquired in the precision stage are synthesized and applied to broader concepts. It is a return to the romance stage, but with the added advantage of classified ideas and relevant techniques. This stage involves the application of principles to concrete detail and is essential for both theoretical interest and practical application, both in complex and in real-world situations.

The document emphasizes that these stages should not be seen as sharply distinct but rather as involving an alternation of dominance, with each stage present throughout the learning process:

Education should consist in a continual repetition of such cycles. Each lesson in its minor way should form an eddy cycle issuing in its own subordinate process. Longer periods should issue in definite attainments, which then form the starting-grounds for fresh cycles. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 30)

Whitehead, thus, not only anticipates Bruner's spiral concept (Bruner, 1960), but was also far ahead of his time. To the best of my knowledge, he was the first to formulate not only the cyclic but also the self-similar structure (Abbott, 2001) of learning processes (Kraler & Schratz, 2012). He describes this as "the rhythmic character of growth" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 43), and also draws conclusions for didactics:

We should banish the idea of a mythical, far-off end of education. The pupils must be continually enjoying some fruition and starting afresh—if the teacher is stimulating in exact proportion to his success in satisfying the rhythmic cravings of his pupils. (Whitehead, 1929, pp. 30-31)

The educational approach should adapt to the stage of the rhythm that the pupils have reached, ensuring that the curriculum is aligned with the natural mental development of the students. Whitehead also stresses that the true goal of education is not merely the accumulation of knowledge but more the cultivation of mental power and the ability to apply principles to new situations. He advocates for a harmonious educational approach that respects the natural rhythms of mental development and prepares students for life's complexities.

1.3. Chapter III – "The Rhythmic Claims of Freedom and Discipline"

In this chapter, Whitehead shifts the perspective of his analysis onto demands resulting from the previous chapter and further explores consequences. As the title indicates, Whitehead is aware of the well-known tension between self-directed freedom and a compulsory curriculum in formal education. He does not explicitly mention Kant in this book (but had a very profound knowledge of his philosophy; cf. Whitehead, 1948, p. 10), and his philosophical position differs from that developed in Kant's concepts (especially on causality; see Whitehead, 1927). But their basic approach to education is very similar. The title of Chapter III of Whitehead's book may indirectly refer to Kant's famous quote from his writings on pedagogy:

One of the greatest problems of education is how to unite submission to the necessary, restraint with the child's capability of constraint exercising his freewill—for restraint is necessary. (Kant, 1900, p. 27)

Whitehead might be thinking of this quote in connection with the title of the Chapter. Kant's and Whitehead's basic approaches to education are surprisingly similar. Whitehead argues, "The only avenue towards wisdom is by freedom in the presence of knowledge. But the only avenue towards knowledge is by discipline in the acquirement of ordered fact. Freedom and discipline are the two essentials of education" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 30). We can compare this with Kant's words, "Man can only become man by education. He is merely what education makes of him" (Kant, 1900, p. 6).

While being aware of the problem of translation, one can argue that even their writing styles seem similar to some extent. In fact, the following argument from Kant more or less covers Whitehead's position:

[T]he greatest and most difficult problem to which man can devote himself is the problem of education. For insight depends on education, and education in its turn depends on insight. It follows therefore that education can only advance by slow degrees, and true conception of the method of education can only arise when one generation transmits to the next its stores of experience and knowledge, each generation adding something of its own before transmitting them to the following. (Kant, 1900, p. 11)

Culture, reason, discipline, development, and freedom (though on the latter they have different positions) are pivotal aspects of education for both of them. They build their argumentation on similar fundamental terms. But Whitehead developed his position just over 100 years later than Kant did. Additionally, Kant focussed more on the external moment of constraint, whereas Whitehead took free development as the initial momentum for individual and collective cultural development.

In his chapter on rhythmic freedom and discipline, Whitehead revisits his stage concept from an administrative and didactic perspective. He criticises traditional education systems for focusing excessively on the accumulation of text-book knowledge, a practice which stifles intellectual curiosity and initiative. Instead, he advocates for a balanced approach that aligns with the natural developmental rhythm of the human mind, consisting of the three stages described above.

Whitehead—like Kant—underscores the importance of self-discipline, guided freedom, and the active utilization of knowledge to cultivate wisdom. He warns against rigid, overly disciplined methods that dull the mind and hinder progress. Education should nurture the whole personality, including its aesthetic and emotional dimensions, to achieve a harmonious development of intellect and character.

Ultimately, Whitehead calls for an education system that begins and ends with freedom, with discipline as a necessary but subordinate phase, ensuring a dynamic and fulfilling learning experience for students. For Whitehead, freedom and discipline are not antagonistic but

complementary. Freedom fosters curiosity and engagement, while discipline ensures the structured acquisition of knowledge. Both must be harmonized to align with the natural growth of the learner's personality.

Most discussions of Whitehead's educational concepts focus solely on the first three chapters, which lay the foundation for his ideas. However, if you want to understand his approach in contextual terms—and learning and education are always contextualised—attention to the chapters following the first three is essential.

2. *Chapters IV – VII: Technical Education, Classics, Curricula, Universities and Beyond*

In Chapters IV-VII, Whitehead discusses specific areas of education and learning, and finally extends the analysis by incorporating fundamental considerations of his process philosophy.

2.1. *Chapter IV – “Technical Education and Its Relation to Science and Literature”*

Throughout his academic career in Cambridge and London, Whitehead taught applied mathematics and supported the curricular development of technical sciences in various positions, believing in the need for a balance between theoretical and practical education. Consequently, Chapter IV explores the nature of technical education and its relationship to science and literature. Whitehead emphasizes once more the need for a balanced and integrated approach to education. He critiques the traditional Platonic ideal of liberal education, which prioritizes intellectual and aesthetic appreciation through the study of literature, art, and philosophy. While acknowledging the contributions of this model to European civilization, such as fostering curiosity and maintaining intellectual dignity, the text argues that it neglects practical and technical skills that are essential for modern life. This demonstrates Whitehead's differentiated reception of fundamental (philosophical) texts, which is always based on a detailed knowledge of the respective authors (like Kant, the British philosophers, and the Greek classics, especially the Pre-Socratic philosophers, and Plato and Aristotle)

On the other hand, Whitehead also discusses the limitations of both liberal and technical education when pursued in isolation. Liberal education, focused on literary and intellectual pursuits, often fails to address the practical needs of society, while technical education, if overly specialized, risks producing narrow-minded individuals lacking intellectual breadth and adaptability. Instead, he advocates for an educational model that combines the strengths of both approaches, ensuring students acquire both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. This integration fosters intellectual vision, creativity, and the ability to apply general principles to specific problems, as presented in Chapters II and III.

Whitehead describes in detail technical education as much more than manual training; it involves a creative process that combines thought and action. It emphasizes the coordination of hand, eye, and mind, enabling students to connect theory with practice:

A technical education is in the main a training in the art of utilising knowledge for the manufacture of material products. Such a training emphasises manual skill, and the co-ordinated action of hand and eye, and judgment in the control of the process of

construction. But judgment necessitates knowledge of those natural processes of which the manufacture is the utilisation. Thus, somewhere in technical training an education in scientific knowledge is required. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 77)

Whitehead criticizes the overemphasis on specialization in education, advocating for a broader approach that highlights general principles and their application across disciplines. He also underscores the role of art and literature in providing intellectual and emotional stimulation, both of which are essential for a healthy and productive life.

The antithesis between a technical and a liberal education is fallacious. There can be no adequate technical education which is not liberal, and no liberal education which is not technical: that is, no education which does not impart both technique and intellectual vision. In simpler language, education should turn out the pupil with something he knows well and something he can do well. This intimate union of practice and theory aids both. The intellect does not work best in a vacuum. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 74)

As his argument shows, Whitehead calls for a better integration of practical-technical and theoretical-artistic content not only for practical or pedagogical reasons. Rather, he assumes that both are constitutively dependent on each other and represent basic anthropological constants of human beings.

2.2. Chapter V – “The Place of Classics in Education”

Whitehead lived in a time of fundamental change, socially (world wars, change of the imperial age, etc.), scientifically (developments in the natural sciences and elsewhere) and technically (communication systems, mobility possibilities, and so on). His own education had been traditional:

On the intellectual side, my education ... conformed to the normal standard of the time. Latin began at the age of ten years, and Greek at twelve. Holidays excepted, my recollection is that daily, up to the age of nineteen and a half years, some pages of Latin and Greek authors were construed, and their grammar examined. Before going to school pages of rules of Latin grammar could be repeated, all in Latin, and exemplified by quotations. The classical studies were interspersed with mathematics. Of course, such studies included history—namely, Herodotus, Xenophon, Thucydides, Sallust, Livy, and Tacitus. I can still feel the dullness of Xenophon, Sallust, and Livy. Of course, we all know that they are great authors; but this is a candid autobiography.

The others were enjoyable. Indeed my recollection is that the classics were well taught, with an unconscious comparison of the older civilization with modern life. I was excused in the composition of Latin Verse and the reading of some Latin poetry, in order to give more time for mathematics. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 9)

Due to fundamental changes in social conditions as well as scientific and technological advances, Whitehead realized that the traditional education system had to change in terms of both content

and didactics. But similar to his argument about the practical and theoretical aspects of knowledge, he argued for both as two necessary sides of the same coin. One cannot be fully developed without the other.

In this Chapter, he discusses—well informed by his own course of education—the historical and contemporary significance of classical studies, during his time particularly of Latin and Greek, in shaping intellectual and cultural development. He emphasizes that the future of classics in education is not solely dependent on the joy they bring to scholars or their utility for academic pursuits, but on their broader relevance to modern education and society.

Whitehead acknowledges and argues that the long era of dominance of the classics in higher education, where they once reigned unchallenged alongside mathematics, has passed, as modern disciplines of widespread interest and practical application have emerged:

There are now other disciplines each involving topics of wide-spread interest, with complex relationships, and exhibiting in their development the noblest feats of genius in its stretch of imagination and its philosophic intuition. Almost every walk of life is now a learned profession, and demands one or more of these disciplines as the substratum for its technical skill. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 61)

At the same time, Whitehead holds the classics in high regard, viewing them as a unique pathway to intellectual development through their insights into logic, philosophy, history, and aesthetics. He viewed the study of Latin and Greek as a means to cultivate analytical thinking, linguistic precision, and an appreciation of literary beauty. Moreover, he describes the process of translation as a rigorous exercise in thought analysis, fostering clarity and depth of understanding.

These fundamental qualities of classical languages face practical challenges that Whitehead was familiar with from his functions:

We must remember that the whole problem of intellectual education is controlled by lack of time. If Methuselah was not a well-educated man, it was his own fault or that of his teachers. But our task is to deal with five years of secondary school-life. Classics can only be defended on the ground that within that period, and sharing that period with other subjects, it can produce a necessary enrichment of intellectual character more quickly than any alternative discipline directed to the same object. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 96)

He therefore advocated for a balanced approach, combining the study of original texts with translation, to ensure accessibility while preserving the richness of the original language. This method should allow students to grasp the broader vision of Rome and Greece, their contributions to European civilization, and their influence on modern thought. So, his curricular goal would be to ensure that classics remain relevant by demonstrating their value in fostering intellectual character and cultural understanding within the limited timeframe of modern education.

To sum it up, Whitehead argues that critical thinking, cultural awareness, and intellectual enrichment largely benefit from classical studies.

2.3. Chapter VI – “The Mathematical Curriculum”

Whitehead had studied mathematics at Cambridge and lectured in the subject (pure and applied mathematics) from at least 1885 (Whitehead, 1948, pp. 10-11) until 1924, when he joined the faculty of Harvard University in the Department of Philosophy. His strong commitment to modernising the teaching of mathematics should therefore come as no surprise.

In this chapter, Whitehead discusses the purpose of mathematics education, emphasizing its role in fostering logical reasoning, abstract thinking, and practical application. He criticizes traditional approaches to teaching mathematics, which often focus on rote memorization of theorems and formulae, and advocates for a reform of the curriculum to prioritize understanding fundamental ideas and their relevance to modern thought:

in education we proceed from the particular to the general. Accordingly, children should be taught the use of [mathematical] ideas by practice among simple examples. My point is this: the goal should be, not an aimless accumulation of special mathematical theorems, but the final recognition that the preceding years of work have illustrated those relations of number, and of quantity, and of space, which are of fundamental importance. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 121)

Whitehead thus anticipates Bruner’s concept of fundamental ideas (basic ideas/fundamental structures) as the cornerstone of curriculum design and didactics. In his ground-breaking *The Process of Education* (1960), Bruner writes,

Students ... have a limited exposure to the materials they are to learn. How can this exposure be made to count in their thinking for the rest of their lives? The dominant view among men who have been engaged in preparing and teaching new curricula is that the answer to this question lies in giving students an understanding of the fundamental structures of whatever subjects we choose to teach. This is a minimum requirement for using knowledge, for bringing it to bear on problems and events one encounters outside a classroom....

[T]he basic ideas that lie at the heart of all science and mathematics and the basic themes that give form to life and literature are as simple as they are powerful. To be in command of these basic ideas, to use them effectively, requires a continual deepening of one’s understanding of them that comes from learning to use them in progressively more complex forms. (pp. 11-13)

To the best of my knowledge, Bruner never quotes Whitehead. Therefore, the similarity in their arguments may come from the logical consequence of their deep knowledge of the educational system and necessary reforms.

In this chapter, Whitehead highlights the importance of using practical examples and applications to illustrate mathematical ideas. He also criticizes the overemphasis on specialized topics, such as the addition formulae in trigonometry or the detailed study of conic sections, which are deemed

unnecessary for general education. Instead, the curriculum should focus on topics that illuminate broader ideas. And ultimately, the chapter calls for a shift in mathematics education to align with the intellectual needs of the modern era. It advocates for a curriculum that balances logical rigor with accessibility, ensuring that students not only acquire technical skills but also develop the capacity to think abstractly and apply mathematical reasoning to diverse fields. It was not until the mid-1990s that these ideas began to be widely discussed in mathematics education. This was particularly the case in Germany (Heymann, 2003).

2.4. Chapter VII – “Universities and Their Function”

Whitehead spent his entire professional life in universities. Critical, concerned with the social responsibility and further development of these institutions, he became aware of the possibilities and limitations of universities in his various academic functions and as a researcher. At Cambridge, he criticized the refusal to admit women to the university. In London, he was concerned with the valorisation of applied sciences. Finally, at Harvard, he was involved in adapting the structure and content of the institution to the demands of a modern, rapidly changing society.

So, in Chapter VII, Whitehead explores the evolving role and function of universities in modern society, emphasizing their critical importance in fostering intellectual and imaginative growth. He argues for the justification of universities in the following way:

The justification for a university is that it preserves the connection between knowledge and the zest of life, by uniting the young and the old in the imaginative consideration of learning. The university imparts information, but it imparts it imaginatively. At least, this is the function which it should perform for society. A university which fails in this respect has no reason for existence....

Imagination is not to be divorced from the facts: it is a way of illuminating the facts. It works by eliciting the general principles which apply to the facts, as they exist, and then by an intellectual survey of alternative possibilities which are consistent with those principles. It enables men to construct an intellectual vision of a new world. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 139)

Whitehead highlights the rapid expansion of universities globally during his time. However, he warns that this growth, if not guided by a clear understanding of the primary functions of universities, risks undermining their usefulness. Whitehead identifies the integration of imagination and experience as a key theme of modern universities. Universities are tasked with nurturing imagination during youth, free from the immediate responsibilities of action, while also fostering disciplined thought. This balance is essential for preparing individuals for their later life.

In London Whitehead supported the then new colleges of science and technology. Ten years later, at Harvard, he discussed the role of business schools as a modern addition to universities, reflecting the intellectualization of business as a vocation. He describes these schools as examples of how universities can adapt to societal needs while maintaining their core mission of imaginative education.

Whitehead lived at a time of profound economic and social change as well as transformation. During his lifetime, the foundations were laid for today's ubiquitous quantification in all areas of life. He was well aware of this transformation. Universities, particularly in the US, were beginning to measure their scientific output.

Whitehead defined universities the following way: "The universities are schools of education, and schools of research" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 92). He saw the two as fundamentally and existentially intertwined. One cannot function successfully without the other. His thoughts, written down 100 years ago, seem more relevant than ever in the current debate on the ranking-oriented, purely quantitative contemporary assessments of universities worldwide.¹ Since he was a mathematician, Whitehead did not argue against quantitative measures. But his final goal was always qualitative, substantial development. What he says seems so clear and central that I would like to quote it in full below:

It must not be supposed that the output of a university in the form of original ideas is solely to be measured by printed papers and books labeled with the names of their authors. Mankind is as individual in its mode of output as in the substance of its thoughts. For some of the most fertile minds composition in writing, or in a form reducible to writing, seems to be an impossibility. In every faculty you will find that some of the more brilliant teachers are not among those who publish. Their originality requires for its expression direct intercourse with their pupils in the form of lectures, or of personal discussion. Such men exercise an immense influence; and yet, after the generation of their pupils has passed away, they sleep among the innumerable unthanked benefactors of humanity. Fortunately, one of them is immortal —Socrates.

Thus it would be the greatest mistake to estimate the value of each member of a faculty by the printed work signed with his name. There is at the present day some tendency to fall into this error; and an emphatic protest is necessary against an attitude on the part of authorities which is damaging to efficiency and unjust to unselfish zeal.

But, when all such allowances have been made, one good test for the general efficiency of a faculty is that as a whole it shall be producing in published form its quota of contributions of thought. Such a quota is to be estimated in weight of thought, and not in number of words. (Whitehead 1929, pp. 148-149).

In summary, Whitehead stresses the importance of faculty as imaginative scholars who inspire students. He criticizes the (then nascent) tendency to measure the value of teaching by published work alone, and emphasizes the irreplaceable impact of direct interaction and intellectual stimulation.

Ultimately, the chapter asserts that universities are vital for societal progress, serving as hubs where the adventure of thought meets the adventure of action. Their success depends on fostering a culture of imagination, collaboration, and intellectual freedom, ensuring their relevance in an ever-changing world.

¹ See for example "World University Rankings 2025" at <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/latest/world-ranking>.

3. *Chapters VIII – X*

3.1. *Chapter VIII – “The Organisation of Thought”*

Chapters I (“The Aims of Education”) and VIII (“The Organisation of Thought”) were among the earliest chapters of the book to be published or presented as addresses, both dating back to 1916 (see Whitehead, 1917, p. vii). Whitehead was 55 years old at the time, had the experience of almost a complete professional lifetime of research and teaching in mathematics behind him, and was already putting together, without publication, his fundamental thoughts on process philosophy. So, Chapter VIII seems to be about ‘putting things together.’ Whitehead specifically explores the intricate relationship between logic, science, and the structuring of human understanding. He emphasizes that organized thought is the foundation of organized action—which is what human beings in an organized society need to have flourish—and that science represents a specific type of thought organization aimed at understanding and explaining the universe:

It is no accident that an age of science has developed into an age of organisation. Organised thought is the basis of organised action. Organisation is the adjustment of diverse elements so that their mutual relations may exhibit some predetermined quality. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 153)

Whitehead also highlights the dual origins of science: the practical source, which seeks to direct actions toward achieving specific goals, and the theoretical source, which arises from the desire to understand the underlying principles of phenomena. Both aspects must, therefore, be present in universities, subject-wise, both in the area of research (theoretical and applied sciences) and in the area of teaching (content and didactics).

The chapter delves into the inductive nature of modern science (Bacon, Mill), because “Science is the organisation of thought” (Whitehead, 1929, p. 103). In line with his philosophical approach, Whitehead interprets science as a process;

Success [in science] is never absolute, and progress in the right direction is the result of a slow, gradual process of continual comparison of ideas with facts. (Whitehead, 1929, pp. 156-157)

For Whitehead, induction, combined with deductive reasoning, forms the backbone of scientific inquiry, as both are essential for deriving meaningful knowledge. The text critiques the historical stagnation of logic, attributing it to an over-reliance on authority and a lack of innovation, which hindered its progress for centuries.

A significant portion of the chapter is devoted to the structure of logical theory, which he divides into four sections: the arithmetic stage, the algebraic stage, the general-function theory stage, and the analytic stage. These stages reflect the progression of thought from simple propositions to complex logical constructions, mirroring the development of mathematical concepts like numbers, functions, and correlations.

Whitehead also addresses the challenges of aligning abstract scientific concepts with the messy, fragmented nature of human experience. He argues that science begins with common-sense thought and experience and then refines and reorganizes it to create precise, interconnected ideas. This process involves both observation and imagination, as well as the formulation of idealized concepts (Whitehead, 1929, p. 159-ff.).

Whitehead finally interprets science as a continuous process of comparing ideas with facts, aiming to construct a coherent understanding of the universe. He states, “Science is a permanent record of premises, deductions, and conclusions, verified all along the line by its correspondence with facts” (Whitehead, 1929, p. 162). Therefore, it calls for a balance between theoretical exploration and practical application, emphasizing that neither can progress without the other.

3.2. Chapter IX – “The Anatomy of Some Scientific Ideas”

Chapter IX contains the longest text in the book. It differs in structure and organisation from the other chapters, containing five parts: I. Facts, II. Objects, III. Time and Space, IV. Fields of Force and V. Conclusion. Here Whitehead explores the foundational principles and methodologies underlying scientific thought and perception. He emphasizes the distinction between physical science and other domains of thought, such as metaphysics and value judgments, which are excluded from scientific inquiry to maintain objectivity and practicality. Focusing on Whitehead’s reflections on education, I will leave this chapter aside, as it mainly delves into metaphysics, ontology, and aspects of Whitehead’s process philosophy.

3.3. Chapter X – “Space, Time, and Relativity”

For an experienced reader of Whitehead, nothing unusual happens in the final chapter. The initial questions, observations, analyses, and conceptualisations begin with a practical and experiential approach. The situation is similar with to that found in “The Aims of Education.” As the pages and chapters progress, the discussion becomes more theoretical, abstract, and philosophical. Eventually, one ends up with very fundamental metaphysical and ontological discussions. This is also the case here.

Whereas in the previous chapter Whitehead argued from the point of view of the physical sciences, here he explores the intricate relationships between space, time, and relativity, examining these concepts from various scientific, philosophical, and psychological perspectives, finally concentrating on ontological and metaphysical aspects of his process philosophy. Educational questions seem to be very far away from this discussion. He ends his analysis with some very relevant remarks in relation to the context of education:

I emphasise the point that our only exact data as to the physical world are our sensible perceptions. We must not slip into the fallacy of assuming that we are comparing a given world with given perceptions of it. The physical world is, in some general sense of the term, a deduced concept. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 247)

In particular, this means that we cannot do without normative concepts in education. A purely empirical approach to education would fall short. Education starts with people and has people as its end. Generalized, as Whitehead always strives to do, this means that “[o]ur problem is ... to fit the world to our perceptions, and not our perceptions to the world” (Whitehead, 1929, p. 165).

Culture is part of us, as is education. We create culture and education. But Whitehead is no radical constructivist. He much more generalizes the pre-Socratic, primarily cosmological reference of philosophy. For him, nature and the world contain all phenomena, let it be in natural sciences, humanities, the outside world, consciousness etc. His approach is—as we have seen—integrative and holistic.

Conclusion

Alfred North Whitehead was a thorough and comprehensive thinker. He was what we would now call competent on a number of levels.

First, as a scientist and researcher as well as being a mathematician and logician, he made fundamental contributions to the further development of these disciplines in the 20th century. The same is true of his work in the field of philosophy, in particular in ontology and metaphysics (process philosophy).

Secondly, as a (university) teacher, he was well aware of the different needs of different groups of students, whether mathematicians or engineering students, math and physics teacher students, etc. His concepts, ideals and didactic demands as discussed in this paper were the result of a profound knowledge of teaching practice. And, as far as we know, he was very successful in this way. Whitehead’s first publication after *Principia Mathematica* (1910) was, for instance, his *An Introduction to Mathematics* in 1911. The book “was published in the series ‘The Home University Library of Modern Knowledge,’ which published concise introductions on a broad range of topics for a general audience” (Hales, 2024, p. 83). Hales compares its scope to Roger Penrose’s successful approach to making fundamental aspects of mathematics and physics more popular and understandable to a wider audience.

Using the teaching of mathematics as a blueprint for teaching in general, Whitehead gives an explanation for and an analysis of the phenomenon of why this area of study often fails to be sustainable and attractive by referring to the concept of fundamental ideas that Bruner (1960) broadly popularized in education 50 years later:

The reason for this failure of the science to live up to its reputation is that its fundamental ideas are not explained to the student disentangled from the technical procedure which has been invented to facilitate their exact presentation in particular instances. Accordingly, the unfortunate learner finds himself struggling to acquire a knowledge of a mass of details which are not illuminated by any general conception. (Whitehead, 1911, p. 8)

Thirdly, during his long academic career, he held a number of academic and administrative positions in which he sought to contribute actively to the reform and development of teaching:

During the later years ... I was Dean of the Faculty of Science in the University, Chairman of the Academic Council which manages the internal affairs concerned with London education, and a member of the Senate. I was also Chairman of the Council which managed The Goldsmith's College, and a member of the Council of the Borough Polytechnic. There were endless other committees involved in these positions. In fact, participation in the supervision of London education, University and Technological, joined to the teaching duties of my professorship at the Imperial College constituted a busy life. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 13)

This threefold professional biographical approach (research, teaching, administration) was the basis for his modelling and conceptualisation of education as well as for his well-founded criticism of existing conditions and his proposals for further development and improvement.

Ultimately, Whitehead's pedagogical considerations are permeated by the concepts of his process philosophy. The seeds of this may lie in his preoccupation with the logical foundations of mathematics, where he saw relations as a fundamental principle. Aware of the profound social changes and developments of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, he was convinced of the need for development in all areas of life. Whitehead saw science and learning as positive means of addressing social, technological, and economic challenges. He believed in the positive contribution of science to solving human problems and challenges, but was not naïve in this respect, as he assumed a specific, responsible scientific way of thinking and acting within science. In terms of his (professional) biography and his achievements and positions, Whitehead is a person of high integrity and authenticity. First, he observed and experienced, then he drew preliminary conclusions, took part in processes, and finally arrived at profound positions. This was usually the starting point for the integration of his findings into the constantly evolving concept of his process philosophy—creating a complete integrity such as we rarely find it in one human being.

If we finally try to summarize his basic educational concepts, the following seven aspects are of fundamental importance:

- The need for a *process-oriented, relational and holistic approach*: in education, different aspects and actors are intertwined in various different ways. This needs to be manifested in thought and action.
- *Avoidance of inert ideas*: education should not focus on the passive reception of disconnected or unutilized ideas. Such inert ideas are not only useless but also harmful, as they fail to stimulate intellectual growth and creativity. Instead, ideas should be tested, applied, and integrated into fresh combinations to remain alive and relevant.
- The *cycles of learning*: education is described as a rhythmic process involving three stages: the “stage of Romance” (initial curiosity and wonder), the “stage of Precision” (discipline and systematic learning), and the “stage of Generalization” (synthesis and broader understanding). These cycles repeat throughout intellectual development, fostering a balance between freedom and discipline.
- *Theory and practice* are constitutively linked to one another.

- *Integration of knowledge:* the curriculum should avoid fragmenting subjects into isolated components, but rather concentrate on fundamental ideas and present knowledge as interconnected and relevant to life, helping students see the woods through the trees. This approach ensures that education reflects the complexity and unity of life.
- *Freedom and discipline:* effective education requires a balance between freedom and discipline. Freedom fosters creativity and curiosity, while discipline ensures focus and precision. Over-disciplinary or rigid structures can dull the mind and stifle intellectual growth, while excessive freedom without structure can lead to aimlessness.
- *Holistic development of the individual:* education should nurture the whole personality, including the intellectual, emotional, and aesthetic dimensions, by fostering a sense of wonder, curiosity, and appreciation for beauty. This ensures a balanced development of character and intellect, enabling students to achieve wisdom and actively apply their knowledge in life. These elements are also essential for intellectual and emotional development, as they inspire deeper engagement with ideas and foster a love for learning.

A well-known standard volume on current learning theories is Knut Illeri's *Contemporary Theories of Learning: Learning Theorists ... in their Own Words* (Illeris, 2018). When reading individual chapters of this book, one has the impression of recognising many of Whitehead's ideas. Details and contexts have changed somewhat. But the basic concepts seem timeless. They are as relevant today as they were when they were written.

We are experiencing our time today as a period of transformation. Process-oriented approaches, profound analysis, competencies and knowledge, responsible collaboration, and above all communication appear to be of paramount importance in meeting the environmental, societal, and technological challenges we face. Whitehead was very interested in Wittgenstein's approach to fundamental questions. But he heavily contradicted early Wittgenstein's seventh and last proposition of the *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* "Whereof one cannot speak, thereof one must be silent" (Wittgenstein, 1922, p. 189). He believed in language:

Philosophy is an attempt to express the infinity of the universe in terms of the limitations of language. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 15)

Whitehead's fundamental approaches and concepts are more relevant today, in a time of change and misinformation, than ever. He is worth reading, especially because "much of Whitehead's philosophy is understandable ... this is especially so of Whitehead's philosophy of education" (Blasius, 1997, p. 303).

References

- Abbott, A. D. (2001). *Chaos of disciplines*. University Of Chicago Press.
- Bacher, S. (2024). Wilhelm von Humboldt's concept of diversity as an integrated component of his idea(1) of Bildung. *Ethics and Education* 19 (2), pp. 168–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17449642.2024.2364554>. Accessed 17 July 2025
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice Hall.
- Blasius, F. R. (1997). Alfred North Whitehead's informal philosophy of education. *Studies in Philosophy and Education* 16 (1), pp. 303–315.
- Bruner, J. (1960). *The process of education*. Harvard University Press.
- Hales, T. (2024). A review of Alfred North Whitehead's "Introduction to Mathematics." *Pittsburgh Interdisciplinary Mathematics Review* 1 (1), pp. 83–89. <https://doi.org/10.5195/pimr.2024.23>. Accessed 17 July 2025.
- Hampe, M. (1998). *Alfred North Whitehead*. Beck.
- Heymann, H.W. (2003). *Why teach mathematics? A focus on general education*. Springer.
- Illeris, K. (2019). *Contemporary theories of learning: Learning theorists ... in their own words*. Routledge.
- Kant, I. (1900). *On Education (Über Pädagogik)*. A. Churton (trans.). D.C. Heath.
- Kraler, C., & Schratz, M. (2013). From best practice to next practice: A shift through research-based teacher education. *Research-Based Teacher Education Reform: Special Issue of Reflecting Education* 8 (2), pp.88-125.
- Piaget, J. (1971). *Genetic epistemology*. W.W. Norton.
- Times Higher Education. (2025). World university rankings 2025. <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/latest/world-ranking>. Accessed 17 July 2025.
- Whitehead, A. N. (1896). On ideals: With reference to the controversy concerning the admission of women to degrees in the university. *Cambridge Review*, pp. 310-311.
- . (1911). *An introduction to mathematics*. Williams and Norgate.
- . (1917). *The organisation of thought: Educational and scientific*. Williams and Norgate.

---. (1925). *Science and the modern world*. MacMillan.

---. (1927). *Symbolism, its meaning and effect*. MacMillan.

---. (1929). *The aims of education and other essays*. MacMillan.

---. (1929/1978). *Process and reality*. Free Press.

---. (1933). *Adventure of ideas*. Free Press.

---. (1938). *Modes of thought*. MacMillan.

---. (1948). *Essays in science and philosophy*. Rider and Company.

Whitehead, A. N. & Russell, B. (1910). *Principia mathematica*. Vol. 1 (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press.

Wittgenstein, L. (1922). *Tractatus logico philosophicus*. Kegan, Trench, Trubner.